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Appendix A: The LTV of the median of $(B - V)_{\text{obs}}$ between 1962 and 2020

Table A.1. Data for the blue dots in the top panel of Fig. 1: reduced JDs and $(B - V)_{\text{obs}}$.

Reduced JD	$(B - V)_{\text{obs}}$	Reduced JD	$(B - V)_{\text{obs}}$
38.00	1.10	51.50	1.45
39.40	1.10	51.90	1.50
40.00	1.05	53.00	1.25
41.50	1.05	53.375	1.28
42.00	1.12	54.00	1.15
44.29	1.35	54.475	1.12
44.80	1.35	55.00	1.10
46.50	1.45	55.40	1.22
46.90	1.40	55.475	1.22
47.50	1.38	55.925	1.20
47.90	1.36	56.15	1.17
48.40	1.25	56.80	1.30
48.50	1.25	57.132	1.25
49.00	1.20	57.50	1.23
49.50	1.44	57.60	1.25
50.20	1.45	58.10	1.25
51.00	1.45	59.00	1.26

Notes. See also Table A.2 for the data of the red dots. To prevent crowding in the figure, T_{eff} -values (green numbers) are only given for a limited number of red dots.

Appendix A.1: General survey of properties of the atmospheres of YHGs

YHGs such as ρ Cas are subject to continuous ordinary quasi-periodic pulsations, and once in a few decades they show an outburst. They can be considered responsible for the global dynamics, and as a result, responsible for the enumerated variations and correlations between all kinds of physical processes. For example, modifications of photometric properties, the T_{eff} , the selective continuum opacity, the luminosity, stellar radius, gas density, mass-loss rate, and the chemical composition of their extended atmospheres.

The pulsations and outbursts are also responsible for one of the most important photometric properties of YHGs discussed in this paper. For example, the variations of the LTV of the median sketched through all pulsations and outbursts. During the compression phases, the increased surface gravity increases the gas density of the extended layers of the outer atmosphere. This alters the selective continuum opacity of different types of atoms and ions for the incoming radiation. They are responsible for optical depth effects and the fluctuations of the median $(B - V)_{\text{obs}}$.

We can conclude that we are dealing with one of the complicated physical properties of YHGs. This is supported by Lobel et al.'s conclusion (2015), that the variable stellar temperature is caused by the quasi-periodic pulsations, strongly correlating with the radial velocities and the photometric parameters. This was the result of a detailed comparative study of selected Fe I absorption lines between 1991 and 1995 in the spectra of HR 5171A, ρ Cas, and HR 8752.

Table A.2. Data for the red dots in the top and bottom panel of Fig. 1

Reduced JD	T_{eff} K	$(B - V)_{\text{obs}}$	$\delta(B - V)$
51.315	5750	1.51	0.72
51.371	6000	1.41	0.68
51.600	7600	1.32	0.77
51.830	4400	1.53	0.00
51.890	4500	1.63	0.10
54.760	6700	1.10	0.46
55.104	6420	1.11	0.41
55.391	5730	1.23	0.46
55.409	5777	1.25	0.47
55.464	6044	1.18	0.45
55.574	6.74	1.17	0.46
55.574	6270	1.19	0.50
55.575	6322	1.17	0.46
55.819	7060	1.21	0.60
55.828	7180	1.18	0.60
55.850	7390	1.19	0.62
55.872	7420	1.18	0.62
56.199	7810	1.10	0.56
56.254	7250	1.20	0.62
56.567	4850	1.35	0.10
56.597	4900	1.42	0.18
57.005	6550	1.23	0.58
57.036	6270	1.32	0.63
57.178	6350	1.28	0.60
57.350	7120	1.18	0.59
57.351	7030	1.18	0.58

Notes. First: the data for the red dots in the top and bottom panel of Fig. 1: reduced JDs, the T_{eff} and the $(B - V)_{\text{obs}}$. Second: for the bottom panel: the $\delta(B - V)$ determining the scale difference between the observed colour index corrected for the ISR, but reddened by the selective continuum opacity, and the colour index of de Jager & Nieuwenhuijzen (1987) 'zero continuum opacity scale' for the colour magnitudes $(B - V)_{\text{dJN}}$ (and we suspect with negligible continuum opacity). To prevent crowding in both panels, Fig. 1 T_{eff} -values are only given for a limited number of red dots.

Appendix A.2: Two partly overlapping time-series in BV of ρ Cas relative to the comparison star

See Table 1. The Appendix Figs. A.1 and A.2 show two different partly overlapping BV time-series of ρ Cas, relative to the same comparison star: HD 223173 = HR 9010 in BV of the Johnson system $V = 5.513$, $B = 7.163$ and $(B - V) = 1.650$. The first time series 2003-2020 Fig. A.1 is by coauthor G.W.H. (Automatic Telescope Projects. His complete tables are available at the CDS, Henry 1995, 1999; see sub-tables Tables Appendix M.1 and M.2 in Paper I).

The second time series 2015-2022, Fig. A.2 is by the AAVSO coauthors E.J.v.B. and M.S. and are available at the AAVSO International Database Data Usage Guidelines¹ as well as the particulars of the comparison stars. In order to make discussion on individual pulsations easy, their maxima are numbered above the pulsation maxima according to the nomenclature explained in Sect. 2.

Figures A.1 & A.2 show from about max6, a decreasing amplitude pattern and a shortening of the periods. A likely forerunner indicating that ρ Cas passed the 8200 K bound-

¹ <https://www.aavso.org/data-usage-guidelines>

ary in order to continue evolving on a blue loop through the YE_V, as supposed by Maravelias & Kraus (2022) a suggestion based on the declining activity of the outbursts. See Sect. 6 of this paper.

Note that the height of the max5 and max6 in Figs. A.1 and A.2 are different. This illustrates the fact that the reliability of such diagrams depends on the number of the observations: the more the better.

Appendix A.3: Formulae for computations

Herewith the particulars necessary for computations, such as the new distance (Paper I, Sect. 2.9.), the IS-extinction and reddening (Paper I, Table 1) and the formulae for ρ Cas as used by Nieuwenhuijzen et al. (2012) for HR 8752. The BC as a function of the s -parameter is presented in de Jager & Nieuwenhuijzen (1987).

The classic distance for ρ Cas is 3.1 ± 0.5 kpc, (Zsoldos & Percy 1991). We prefer a shorter distance (Paper I, Sect. 2.9): 2.5 ± 0.3 kpc.

$$A_v = 1.44, E(B - V) = 0.45 \text{ (Paper I: Table 1).}$$

$$M_{\text{bol}} = 4.64 - 2.5 \log L/L_{\odot}$$

$$\log L/L_{\odot} = 0.4(4.64 - M_{\text{bol}})$$

$$\log R/R_{\odot} = 8.47 - 0.2M_{\text{bol}} - 2 \log T_{\text{eff}}$$

Appendix A.3.1: The atypical behaviour of the 2013 outburst of ρ Cas

Kraus et al. (2019) suggested that increased global dynamical activity can be responsible for changing the optical depth i.e. the apparent stellar radius. Indeed, the 2013-outburst stopped declining in V after a descend of only $0^{\text{m}}5$, while normally the depths should be twice as large (Appendix E, Table E.2). Two measured temperatures near the 2013 min1 turned out to be about 4900 K and 4850 K, thus, not as low as 4400 K, but yet TiO bands were present. Thus, the opacity was still not yet zero and apparently sufficiently dense to cause such an optical depth effect. A factor of two shortening the depth of min1 is rather large. It might mean that the descent right after the outburst at max1, happened much slower than usual, contrary to the temperature. Thus after a $0^{\text{m}}5$ decline only, the temperature had almost reached the minimum temperature of ~ 4850 K.

The above is somehow related to the atypical pulsation behaviour of ρ Cas between about 2010 and 2016 (Fig. 3 Kraus et al. 2013; and in this paper: Appendix A: Figs. A.1 and A.2). Some pulsations preceding max1 are atypical as well and temperatures of the maxima are high, up to 7000 K-8000 K). Nevertheless, max1 as well as the descend to min1 look normal. However, the amplitude from max1 to min1 was about twice smaller than other outbursts and the ascending branch to max2 lasted a few hundred days, showing many bumps and shoulders along the first part, including a number of pulsations thereafter, with high temperatures until max5.

Most surprising was the behaviour of the V_{rad} during the ascending branch (Kraus et al. 2019, Fig. 3). It showed an expansion phase along the upper part of the ascending branch to max2, instead of a contraction as it should, meaning that the radius suggested an increase instead of a contraction. This is opposite to normal outbursts such as the one in 2000 (Lobel et al. 2003).

The likely explanation is that an optical thin shell was expelled at max2, but apparently still too transparent to dominate the brightness and spectrum. The many small bumps and shoulders during the first part of the ascending, suggest small types of mass-loss outbursts up to the pulsations hereafter up to max5 and max6 (Appendix A: Figs. A.1 & A.2). It is thinkable that the welling up of hot convection cells were the source of these low-scale mass-loss outbursts, and also responsible for the atypical morphological differences of a number of pulsations.

Appendix A.3.2: The decreasing trend of ρ Cas outbursts and pulsations

Based on an elaborated photometric analysis of the four outbursts: 1946, 1986, 2000, and 2013, Maravelias & Kraus (2022) reported a decreasing trend in the durations, amplitudes as well as shorter time intervals between the outbursts. The 2013-outburst was independently discovered by Aret et al. (2016), and in Paper I: Fig. 2, (because of its much deeper minimum than normal pulsations). Maravelias & Kraus (2022) suggested that ρ Cas may soon pass to the following evolutionary phase. An interesting suggestion which became true.

Our knowledge of outburst properties are mainly based on photoelectric photometry and sometimes differ from those defined of Maravelias & Kraus (2022), which are based on a mix of visual and photoelectric photometry. Nevertheless, our list of photometric outburst properties, also show on the average a declining activity, see Appendix E, Table E.2. Indeed there is also an obvious tendency of decreasing light and colour curve amplitudes in BV after pulsation No. 6, (Fig. A.2 see Table 1).

In Appendix D of Sect. 6 a discussion is presented on ρ Cas' start of the dynamical instability just after the 2000-outburst, leading to the 2013-outburst and the decrease of pulsation periods and amplitudes of light and colour curves.

Appendix A.3.3: The very red 2000-outburst max1 of ρ Cas

A peculiarity is that $(B - V)_{\text{obs}}$ of the max1 of the 2000-outburst with a temperature of 7600 K, amounts to $1^{\text{m}}3$. Corrected for the interstellar reddening $0^{\text{m}}45$ $(B - V)_0 = 0.85$, which is much too red by $\sim 0^{\text{m}}7$, while one would expect $\sim 0^{\text{m}}15$ (the intrinsic colour index for a star of $T_{\text{eff}} = 7600$ K). There currently is no obvious explanation for the large circumstellar reddening we observe during the 2000-outburst. We think however that during this strong outburst phase with accelerated atmospheric expansion the global mass-loss rate strongly increased (Lobel et al. 1998; Gorlova et al. 2006). This expansion rapidly cools down the entire outer atmosphere, thereby decreasing the local gas kinetic temperature T_{kin} and increasing the local gas density of neutral hydrogen. This could be linked to an increase in the number density of H^- -anions which changes the continuum opacity. The fast global atmospheric expansion increases the circumstellar reddening, in part also due to the increase of wind opacity with the formation of di-atomic molecules (e.g., TiO) in the outer atmosphere. We exclude any contributions from dust opacity since T_{kin} in the outer atmosphere is still too high (for $T_{\text{eff}} \simeq 4500$ K) in order to sustain the condensation of dust particles (typically for T_{kin} below ~ 1500 K).

Fig. A.1. The 2003-2020 time series of ρ Cas by G.W.H. in V , B and $(B - V)$ relative to the comparison star HD 223173 see Appendix A.2. We show in Fig. A.1 the median, representing the LTVs, sketched through all ordinary pulsations, as well as the outbursts, including the 2013-one. The numbering on the right in the (explained in Sect. 2) is necessary for identification purposes in the text, just like the irregular red numbering on the left copied from Fig. 2 in Paper I. The red numbering 1 to 10 is necessary as they depict the peculiar pulsations of pulsation maxima between the 2000 and 2013 outbursts. The 2004 minimum marks the moment that warned Lobel that a possible outburst was approaching.

Appendix A.3.4: On HD 179821

Arkhipova et al. (2009) presume that the very vast UBV brightness variations of HD 179821, running in opposite directions, are due variations of the continuum formation level (optical depth variations), by variable mass loss episodes and related temperature variations. Despite the doubt about its genuine type of variable star, whether or not it is a YHG, we find that its mean amplitude ratio $\text{Ampl } V / \text{Ampl } (B - V)$ for 14 selected normal pulsations amount to 1.7 ± 0^m5 (st.dev), similar to those of ρ Cas and HR 8752 (Paper I, Conclusion 3, Appendix D). At least six pulsations of HD 179821 show different ratios, due to high mass loss rates, confirmed by $H\alpha$ emission profiles. We suggest that HD 179821 is a YHG, similar to ρ Cas and HR 8752 (see Fig. A.4).

The UBV -observations of HD 179821 by Arkhipova et al. (2001, 2009), Le Coroller et al. (2003), and Hrivnak et al. (1989, 2001), are plotted in Paper I: Figs. 9 and 10. Such fascinating events as described at the beginning of this section, were also observed at about JD 24 49200 and 24 50200 lasting at most a few months. We plotted a detailed diagram of V versus $(B - V)$ variations (observations based on the four papers mentioned above and of the Hipparcos satellite). Apparently, very fast UBV brightness variations running in opposite directions are caused by small scale active regions in the photosphere suffering of short time scale episodic mass-loss outbursts. So far they were not seen in the light and colour curves of YHGs. We speculate that

HD 179821 is a YHG or a more massive late-type predecessor of a YHG.

Conclusions:

1.- (1) and (2). It appears that a relation between the too weak 2013-outburst and many atypical pulsation properties exists such as those just before during and after the 2013-outburst until max3 and further. We can add the many atypical bumps and shoulders along the ascend to max2 and subsequently along the ascend and decline of many pulsation light curves. Also atypical was the V_{rad} -curve of part of the ascending branches to max1, max2 and max3 in Fig. 3 of Kraus et al. (2019), showing an expansion instead of a contraction, pointing to expanding shells. Obviously, they became dominant in the spectrum. The numerous secondary bumps and shoulders were presumably small scale convection cells responsible for local mass-loss outbursts. Furthermore, the pulsations after pulsation No. 6 show decreasing periods and amplitudes: a confirmation of the highly dynamical instability, a preparation for the next evolutionary phase like HR 8752 did since the 70s, see Figs. A.1, by G.W.H. and Figs. A.2 and E.5., by E.J.v.B. and M.S. According to experience it will still last a couple of decades before ρ Cas shall start to cross the YEV as a smaller, hotter stable star, until the next phase. According to de Jager et al. (2001) this could well be an S Dor variable. However, this only will happen after a couple of decades.

3.- (3). The colour index $(B - V)_0 = 0.85$ of max1 of the 2000-outburst is too red by about 0^m7 . It should be about 0^m15 normal for a temperature of 7600 K. A possible expla-

Fig. A.2. The 2015-2023 time-series (BV) of ρ Cas by the AAVSO observers E.J.v.B. (photoelectric photometry, large dots) and Sblewski (CCD observations, small dots). All relative to the same comparison star as used for Fig. A.1. The sketch of the LTVs (large dots have more weight) starts halfway pulsation No. 3, and continues to No. 12. Due to a too limited number of observations (climate not favourable for unlimited monitoring), the V -curve often shows no very obvious pulsations therefore we omitted them. Standard deviations derived by the observers: for $B = 0^m13$, $V = 0^m09$, $(B - V) = 0^m10$. It appears that in 2023 ρ Cas is still not stable and that the observed mean magnitudes and colour index of ρ Cas amount to: $V_{\text{obs}} = 4.41$, $B_{\text{obs}} = 5.66$, and $(B - V)_{\text{obs}} = 1.25$. These values do not differ much from the extrapolations of the plotted median photometric parameters presented in Paper I Figs. 11 & 12. The same is the case for the present photometric parameters of HR 8752 in Fig. E.5

nation is an increased number of H^- -anions, responsible for the continuum opacity. It depends on the local changes of T_{kin} and the gas density, speculating that this temperature is much too high for dust particles to condensate (at about 1500 K). It turns out that the other outburst maxima are too red by approximately the same amount.

4.- (4). Ikonnikova et al.(2018) suggested that HD 179821 could be a YHG. If true our speculation in Paper I, Sect. 3.1, Fig. 8, that an outburst could have taken place between 1925 and 1960 is likely.

Appendix B: The construction of four temperature calibration relations

Appendix B.1: An exercise to get used to the 4T method to find a reliable T_{eff} .

It is impossible to determine T_{eff} from concrete B and V magnitudes measured at a specific epoch, because of the presence of the variable selective continuum opacity in the atmosphere of Ia+ yellow hypergiants (discovered in our 2019 Paper I). Therefore, the four calibrated T_{eff} relations in Fig. 2 (an enlargement is advisable) are supposed to be slightly affected by the selective opacity (Sect. 2).

Spectroscopically determined T_{eff} are almost independent from that type of opacity, only the kind of technique

used by different spectroscopists may cause small, but unknown differences.

At the time of the pioneering studies by de Jager & Nieuwenhuijzen (1987) and Nieuwenhuijzen & de Jager (2000), the presence of the disturbing influence of the selective continuum opacity in the atmospheres of the used super- and hypergiants, was unknown (Sects. 2 and 3). In their appendices they offer an unequivocal relation between the T_{eff} , the analytical variable s and the reddening free, $(B - V)$, which we use to write as $(B - V)dJN$. We assume that it is not free from some selective continuum opacity.

We have selected arbitrarily one sequence BV observations from Table B.2., to be used for deriving the temperatures T_{eff} and offer a step-by-step explanation to find them. Use the tables published in the Appendices of both papers.

Step 1. It is necessary to construct on graphic paper the relations for Ia+ hypergiants between T_{eff} and s , and between $(B - V)dJN$ and s from the tables by de Jager & Nieuwenhuijzen and Nieuwenhuijzen & de Jager mentioned above.

Step 2: from Table B.2.: use the data listed at Red.JD 55872. Bracketed numbers below (1) to (4) are used for the parameters necessary to find the effective temperatures simply called T .

Notes: Your results may differ from the ones listed in Table B.2., but that is not alarming as the intrinsic scatter

Table B.1. The T_{eff} and the photometric data used in Fig. 2.

Set	Red.JD	T_{eff} (K)	V_{obs}	B_{obs}	$(B - V)_{\text{obs}}$	s	$(B - V)dJN$
Lo	49343	7250	4.45	5.80	1.35	3.76	0.13
	51315	5750	4.72	6.23	1.51	4.54	0.34
	51371	6000	4.67	6.08	1.41	4.40	0.28
	51600	7600	4.26	5.58	1.32	3.59	0.12
	51830	4500	5.28	6.81	1.53	5.29	1.08
	51890	4500	5.10	6.73	1.63	5.29	1.08
Kl	54760	6744	4.61	5.71	1.10	4.01	0.17
	55104	6420	4.53	5.64	1.11	4.18	0.21
	55409	5777	4.72	5.97	1.25	4.53	0.33
	55464	6044	4.56	5.74	1.18	4.38	0.27
	55574	6174	4.58	5.75	1.17	4.31	0.25
	55575	6322	4.57	5.74	1.17	4.23	0.23
Kr	55394.5	5730	4.74	5.97	1.25	4.55	0.34
	55574.6	6270	4.57	5.75	1.18	4.26	0.24
	55819.6	7060	4.53	5.74	1.21	3.86	0.15
	55828.5	7180	4.52	5.70	1.18	3.80	0.14
	55850.5	7390	4.49	5.68	1.19	3.69	0.12
	55872	7420	4.50	5.68	1.18	3.68	0.11
	56136	7920	4.33			3.45	0.08
	56143	8000	4.32			3.41	0.07
	56199	7810	4.41	5.52	1.11	3.50	0.09
	56254	7250	4.56	5.76	1.20	3.76	0.13
	56567	4850	4.79	6.14	1.35	5.06	0.82
	56597	4900	4.84	6.26	1.42	5.03	0.78
	57005	6550	4.41	5.64	1.23	4.11	0.20
	57060	6270	4.46	5.78	1.32	4.26	0.24
	57178	6350	4.67	5.95	1.28	4.22	0.23
	57350	7120	4.43	5.61	1.18	3.83	0.14
	57351	7030	4.43	5.61	1.18	3.87	0.15
	56136	7920	4.33			3.45	0.08
	56143	8000	4.32			3.41	0.07
	56199	7810	4.41	5.52	1.11	3.50	0.09
	56326	6820	4.51			3.98	0.17
	57186	6510	4.70			4.14	0.20
	57191	6730	4.65			4.02	0.18
	57199	6850	4.65			3.96	0.16
57213	7020	4.57			3.88	0.15	
57224	7060	4.59			3.86	0.15	
55627	7330	4.45			3.72	0.12	
55669.6	7360	4.35			3.71	0.12	
55795	6640	4.50			4.07	0.19	
55809	6910	4.50			3.93	0.16	
55816	7060	4.45			3.86	0.15	

in the various diagrams is large, and personal preferences by reading off the temperatures from the calibration relations counts as well.

The interstellar reddening correction used amounts to 0^m45 .

Step 3.: Derive T_{eff} for the observed parameters V , $(B - V)$ and B from the first, third (!) and second calibration relation (Fig. 2), respectively. Then find with the aid of the fourth calibration relation in Fig. 2 the $(B - V)dJN$.

Observed parameters:

$$V_{\text{obs}} = 4.50 \quad (1)$$

$$B_{\text{obs}} = 5.68 \quad (3)$$

$$(B - V)_{\text{obs}} = 1.18 \quad (2)$$

Results for temperatures: $T(1) = 7050 \text{ K}$, $T(2) = 7250 \text{ K}$, $T(3) = 7250 \text{ K}$

$(B - V)_{(0)} = 1.18 - 0.45 = 0.73$, according to the fourth calibration relation in Fig. 2: $(B - V)dJN = 0.13$,

With the aid of the $(B - V)dJN/s$ diagram: $s(4) = 3.76$ and with the aid of the T_{eff}/s diagram: Result $T(4) = 7250 \text{ K}$ (4)

The average of the four temperatures (1) (2) (3) and (4): 7050, 7250, 7250 and 7250 K results in $4TK = 7200 \text{ K} \pm 100 \text{ K}$.

Compare this with the $T_{\text{eff}} = 7420 \text{ K}$ by Kraus et al. (2019): thus, difference: $T4$ (short for $4TK$) - $T_{\text{eff}} = 7200 - 7420 = -220 \text{ K}$.

Table B.2. Table for testing the reliability of the 4T method.

Red.JD	V_{obs}	B_{obs}	$(B - V)_{\text{obs}}$	$(B - V)_{\text{dJN}}$	4TK	T_{eff} K	$T4 - T_{\text{eff}}$ K
5394.5	4.72	5.97	1.25	0.35	5525 ± 155	5750	-225
5574.6	4.56	5.75	1.19	0.28	6218 ± 211	6270	- 52
5819.6	4.53	5.74	1.21	0.16	6952 ± 55	7060	-108
5828.5	4.52	5.70	1.18	0.13	7238 ± 165	7180	+ 58
5850.5	4.49	5.68	1.19	0.14	7155 ± 88	7390	-235
5872.0	4.50	5.68	1.18	0.13	7200 ± 100	7420	-220
6199.0	4.42	5.52	1.10	0.03	7990 ± 425	7810	+180
6254.0	4.56	5.76	1.20	0.15	6940 ± 113	7250	-310
6567.0	4.79	6.14	1.35	0.79	5300 ± 302	4950	+450
6597.0	4.84	6.26	1.42	0.79	4925 ± 272	4900	+ 25
7005.0	4.41	5.64	1.23	0.18	7092 ± 424	6550	+542
7036.0	4.57	5.78	1.32	0.29	6278 ± 521	6270	+ 8
7350.0	4.43	5.61	1.18	0.13	7338 ± 103	7120	+218

Notes. The selected data used for the reliability test to determine T_{eff} . The first and second line belong to the K1 set, the other ones to the Kr set. The $(B - V)_{\text{dJN}}$ and opacity is found with the aid of the fourth $(B - V)_0 = ((B - V)_{\text{obs}} - 0.045)$ and by applying Fig. 2 (bottom right). T4 in the last column is short for 4T K.

Fig. A.3. The diagram $\delta(B - V)$ vs. T_{eff} used for the bottom panel of Fig. 1. Note the short overlap between the sets of Kr (small dots) and the K1 set (large dots).

Appendix C: The domain of the LTVs of $(B - V)_0$ 1962-2020, and their zigzag tracks on the HR-diagram

In Table C.1. we provide data sets used in Figs. 1. and 4.

Appendix D: The 2008-2017 time series of ρ Cas on the HR-diagram

Appendix D.1: ρ Cas' start of the dynamical instability, just after the 2000-outburst

This appendix text belongs to Sect. 6 and Fig. 5. To discuss Fig. 5, we need the time-series of G.W.H. in Paper I, Fig. 2.

Fig. A.4. Pulsations of HD 179821 between JD 2450220 and JD2450240. Consult the many papers to which we refer in Appendix A.3.4 on HD 179821. Apparently very fast brightness variations, running from bottom to top and from top to bottom, are caused by small scale active photospheric regions suffering of short time mass-loss outbursts. The top black line means that the mass-loss outbursts go left to the top of the line and on the lower black line go left to the bottom. The measurements of V and B-V are as directly observed, so not in comparison to a reference star.

As at the time, we were ignorant about the fact that the sequence of ordinary pulsations between the outbursts of 2000 and 2013 were exceptional abnormal. After all, ρ Cas was on its way to cross the ~ 8000 K boundary. Therefore, we selected them arbitrary and numbered them from 1 to 10 to analyse their photometric properties. We copied this numbering in red in the $\Delta(B)$ panel of Fig. A.1. of the present paper.

[Note that in Paper I, Tables 2 & 3, we used to write: T(Sp), T(SK), and T(dJN); in the present paper they should be written as T_{eff} , T(SK) means the T_{eff} of Schmidt-Kaler (1982), and T_{eff} , respectively.]

A photometric analysis of a number of pulsations in Fig. A.1. between 2000 and 2013 show large morphological

Table C.1. Luminosity and T_{eff} , the latter based on the 4T method (Sect. 3), of the red dots defining the LTVs of $(B - V)_{\text{obs}}$ in Fig. 1 upper panel, and plotted on the HR-diagram in Fig. 4.

$\log L/L_{\odot}$	$\log T_{\text{eff}}$	Notes
5.42	3.837	
5.42	3.837	
5.40	3.582	
5.40	3.852	
5.39	3.817	
5.44	3.827	
5.42	3.819	
5.34	3.784	med 1986
5.44	3.831	
5.42	3.808	
5.38	3.830	
5.44	3.836	
5.42	3.827	
5.44	3.848	
5.42	3.812	
5.40	3.802	
5.42	3.806	
5.38	3.795	
5.32	3.767	med 2000
5.41	3.797	
5.40	3.813	
5.41	3.814	
5.41	3.823	
5.41	3.835	
5.40	3.810	
5.40	3.825	
5.40	3.837	
5.42	3.842	
5.40	3.804	med 2013
5.41	3.833	
5.40	3.820	
5.42	3.835	
5.45	3.827	
5.44	3.838	
5.42	3.824	

variations, typical for those situated close around the 2013-outburst: striking alternating amplitudes and light curves with secondary bumps and peaks. We mention a few in chronological order: the pulsations numbered 7 (2004), 5 (2010), and 2 (2011). Their striking morphological variations do not happen during stable sequences of the ordinary quasi-periodic pulsation sequences.

The light curves No. 2 with No. 5, represent a peculiar duo, showing a striking high amplitude between the two. Besides, both showed a secondary feature in the ascending branch (typical for the ascending branch of the 2013-outburst and for a number of pulsations thereafter), looking like a plateau and lasting a couple of months. Additionally, pulsation No. 2, discussed and depicted in great detail in Fig. 4 of Paper I, shows on top of its plateau a dome shaped bubble, for which a reliable temperature has now been computed. Only high quality photometry is able to present such detailed light curves (by G.W.H.).

This bubble, perhaps a hot convection cell, which occurred at reduced JD 55515, November 2010, lasted 37 d. The amplitudes amounted to $0^{\text{m}}08$ in B and $0^{\text{m}}05$ in V . The plateau lasted about 100 d. However, it is very difficult

Table D.1. Table for Fig. 5, similar to Fig. 4, but now for the time interval 2008-2017, including the 2013-outburst.

$\log L/L_{\odot}$	$\log T_{\text{eff}}$	Notes
5.38	3.829	
5.41	3.808	
5.34	3.758	
5.35	3.762	
5.39	3.781	
5.395	3.791	
5.40	3.801	
5.47	3.865	
5.51	3.865	$\sim \text{max-1}$
5.42	3.822	
5.42	3.839	
5.44	3.849	
5.41	3.849	
5.43	3.856	
5.45	3.869	
5.455	3.870	
5.55	3.899	
5.56	3.903	$\sim \text{max0}$
5.51	3.892	
5.42	3.860	$\sim \text{min0}$
5.41	3.834	
5.57	3.911	max1
5.40	3.804	median
5.40	3.686	$\sim \text{min1}$
5.37	3.690	min1
5.49	3.863	max2
5.47	3.816	
5.405	3.797	
5.54	3.903	max3
5.58	3.906	max5

to localize it in Fig. 3 of Kraus et al. (2019), because of the large scale difference. The attempt in Paper I to compute a temperature and physical parameters for the maximum of the bubble from the $(B - V)_0$, failed at the time, resulting in an unlikely low temperature: 5040 K. However, with the aid of the 4T method (Sect. 3), this paper, the correct T_{eff} of the top of the bubble turned out to be 6800 ± 350 K, which is of the same order as most temperatures in the 2013-outburst domain. It is also in agreement with the Klochkova et al. (2014) temperature of the plateau at a lower brightness: 6044 K.

An almost similar type of bubble emerged on the top of pulsation No. 3, about 1800 d prior to No. 2, at reduced JD 53740, 2005/2006. It lasted 65 d and the amplitudes amounted to $0^{\text{m}}12$ in B and $0^{\text{m}}07$.

A.L. noticed after the 2000-outburst that pulsation No. 7 of 2004 showed a very deep brightness minimum compared to the regular pulsations, and considered the possibility of a new upcoming (and possibly stronger) outburst event, for example mentioned in Lobel (2004). This observation was accurate since pulsation No. 7 (2004) was the very first pulsation succeeding the massive 2000-outburst, showing strong dynamical instability. We calculated its amplitude ratio, turning out abnormally high: $\text{Ampl } V / \text{Ampl } (B - V) = 2.4$, while for normal pulsations it amounts to 1.7 (see Sect. 2.6 of Paper I). This means that $(B - V)$ was too red due to enhanced mass-loss episodes and hence, due to enhanced selective continuum opacity.

For a number of other pulsation thereafter, until the 2013-outburst, we also find evidence for dynamical instability. This is supported with Fig. 7, ‘the four panel diagram’ of Sect. 8.2. It is most relevant to observe the detailed time-series of ρ Cas in 2015-2023, depicted in this paper in Fig. A.2 (by E.J.v.B. and M.S., Table 1). The time-series started with the pulsation max3 (2015)/2016 (see also Fig. A.1).

It is obvious that ρ Cas still showed dynamical instability, because of its decreasing pulsation amplitudes. This behaviour started with pulsation max4 (2016) and became definitive with max7 (2019). Thus more or less similar to the one of HR 8752 from 1976 up to at least 1994 (Fig. E.4).

Appendix E: The 1986, 2000 and 2013 ρ Cas outburst tracks on the HR-diagram

Table E.1. Table for the three outburst tracks 1986, 2000, and 2013. If known, the max0 and min0 of an ordinary pulsations prior to the outburst are also tabulated.

JD- Date	$\log T_{\text{eff}}$	$\log L/L_{\odot}$	name
240 0000			
46260 1985	3.860	8.47	max1
46470 1986	3.784	5.34	med
46525 1986	3.667	5.34	min1
46850 1987	3.891	5.57	max2
51025 1998	3.940	5.51	max0
51299 1999	3.760	5.33	min0
51600 2000	3.881	5.56	max1
51900 2001	3.767	5.32	med
51830 2000	3.644	5.27	min1
52000 2001	3.832	5.36	max2
56143 2012	3.903	5.55	max0
56240 2012	3.860	5.42	min0
56430 2013	3.911	5.57	max1
56680 2014	3.804	5.40	med
56567 2013	3.686	5.40	~ min1
56597 2013	3.690	5.37	min1
56965 2014	3.863	5.49	max2

Appendix E.1: Light and colour curves of outbursts show morphological differences. The transformation from $(V - R)_0$ to $(B - V)_0$

We discuss the 1986 outburst ρ Cas in Fig. E.1.

the 2013 outburst ρ Cas also in Fig. E.1.

the 2000 outburst ρ Cas in Fig. E.2.

the 2000 outburst ρ Cas in Fig. E.3.

In Sect. 7 of the main text we present an explanation for the twists and bumps in all light- and colour-curves of the outbursts, including the one of 1946. Morphological differences are discussed, see for observers, literature etc. Table 1.

A complete coverage of UBV in 1986 and (BV) in 2013 was regrettably not possible. Therefore, dotted curves in the gaps represent the presumable trends of light and colour curves. In incidental cases it appeared useful to use a transformation formula between $(B - V)_0$ and $(V - R)_0$. We then used the one of Sheffer & Lambert (1992):

$$(V - R)_0 = 0.751(B - V)_0.$$

It appears that almost all types of luminous stars (taken from the list of bright stars by Barnes et al. 1978) do fit this relation, and even fit its linear extension (apart from the M-type giants).

Part of the visual (V) light curve of 1986 is based on the one presented by Lobel et al. (2003). The minimum is approximately at JD 24 46525 with $V \sim 5^{\text{m}}15$. The expected differences between descending and ascending branches can be illustrated with an example of the 1986-outburst in Fig. E.1. To help the eye a few vertical and horizontal lines are drawn in the diagram. The letters a (descending branch), b and c (ascending branch), and the numbers 2 and 3 in min1 mark the peculiar twist. These twists and bumps are discussed and explained in Sect. 7.

The morphological differences between both light and colour curves are obvious. See for the details of the four outbursts of ρ Cas Table E.2 (the one of 1946 in photographic magnitudes).

It appears that the $(B - V)_0$ at maximum light V_{max} is much too red: $0^{\text{m}}80$ instead of $\sim 0^{\text{m}}15$, considering the temperature of 7600 K (Lobel et al. 2003). The cause is a high selective continuum opacity (Appendix A.3.3).

The opposite axis of the $(V - R)_0$ in Fig. E. 3. depicts the $(B - V)_0$ scale. The transformation was possible thanks to the fact that part of the ascending branch of the 1986-outburst was simultaneously observed in BV and in VRI . This transformation appeared to be almost similar to the empirical one derived by Sheffer & Lambert (1992), but only within the range $(B - V)_0 = 0^{\text{m}}$ and $0^{\text{m}}73$, while ρ Cas is redder.

Appendix E.2: Some comments on Fig. E.4

Almost at the same date of the period decline: 1976 in Fig. E.4, the brightness V and the colour index $(B - V)$ became weaker and bluer, respectively (see Fig. 6 & 7 of Paper I), an increasing temperature, and surface gravity, but a decreasing radius and luminosity (Nieuwenhuijzen et al. (2012); see for T their Figs. 2, 5, and 10, for g Fig. 3 and Table 4).

Fig. E.1. Two observed outburst light curves of ρ Cas of 1986 (in UBV) and in BV for 2013 show the morphological differences of the light- and colour-curves. Gaps in the light- and colour-curves are shown with dots. The Julian date of the light minima in V (5.15m) and $(B - V)$ of the 1986-outburst is JD 24 46525, thus to the left of locations 2 and 3 in the $(B - V)$ -curve. Note that the $(B - V)$ -scale of 1986 is twice the V and $(U - B)$ scale. The many peaks and bumps in the 2013 curve are unusual and points to strong atmospheric dynamical activity. They occur during the slow ascend right after a very short lasting min1 (~ 40 d). See for more details in the light curve see Fig. 3 of Kraus et al. (2019) and Maravelias & Kraus (2022). They transformed their visual AAVSO light curve to the V -band, but they are omitted in this figure

Appendix E.3: Interfering pulsations in outbursts?

This question only makes sense if both are caused independently from each other e.g., pulsations by some region in the interior. We know that YHG outbursts are triggered by the release of a large amount of hydrogen ionization-recombination energy. This gives rise to a different kind of atmospheric expansion and contraction mechanism. In view of the duration of outburst, the chance that a pulsation cycle coincides an outburst is not nil. After all, outbursts last 400 d (2000) to 720 d (1946) (Table E.2), and the ordinary quasi-periodic pulsations usually much less: 150-500 d. Any type of interference, say because of the huge size of the star in the outburst phase might be able to change the pulsation cadence and amplitudes just after the outburst (max2). Note that the pulsations prior to the outbursts are generally large normal radial pulsations (see Sect. 8). So far we did not observe abnormal morphological features prior to the outbursts.

Therefore, it is of interest to list peculiar photometric features, occurring during and after outbursts. Those of the 2013-outburst were already discussed in Appendix A.3.1 and Appendix A.3.2, but are intrinsic as ρ Cas was dynamically unstable. We also inspected the light and colour curves

of other outbursts of ρ Cas, of HR 8752, and of HR 5171A. They are listed below:

1.- A quite unique example is offered by HR 5171A: the start and min1 of the Dean-1975-outburst was missed by the observer Dean, but not the ascending branch and max2, numbered No .6 in Fig. 1 of van Genderen (1992). Then immediately followed by a second very high (amplitude 0^m7 in V), numbered No .7, almost on top of No. 6, without a proper minimum in between, and towering high above all other pulsations thereafter! This is unique. A massive shell ejection during this event has been proposed in Paper I (Sect. 3.4.2 and Appendix J). This is supported by presumed presence of an extended dust and molecular envelope as suggested by Chesneau et al. (2014, Sect. 4.1) and by Wittkovski et al. (2017a., b., and c.), and Paper I, (Sect. 2.9). Additionally, a causal connection between pulsation No. 7 and the proposed shell ejection above, was provided by Walraven $VBLUW$ photometry of Pel (1978) during the very steep ascend (in 1977) to the maximum of pulsation No. 7 (in Fig. 1 of van Genderen 1992). It showed an exceptional high ultra-violet excess near about 3838\AA , which is identified as due to an emission feature by neutral aromatic hydrocarbon molecules (PAHs), 37 y later. This was possible thanks to the discovery of such molecules by

Fig. E.2. The light curves of the 2000-outburst of ρ Cas in VRI (Johnson system) relative to the comparison star HD 223173 (by G.W.H.'s ATP Project). Dashed portions are gaps in the time series. Four spectroscopic temperatures T_{eff} (of Lobel et al. 2003) are indicated.

Vijh et al. (2004) in the Red Rectangle Nebula (analysis and discussion of the ultra-violet excess by van Genderen et al. 2015).

2.- Shortly after the 2000-outburst of HR 5171A, (Note: the same year as the 2000-outburst of ρ Cas) two high pulsations towered above the max2, with very large amplitudes amounting to $0^{\text{m}}.6$ and $0^{\text{m}}.8$; see the light curve of Otero depicted in Fig. 3 by Chesneau et al. (2014). This feature was also unique and reminiscent of the case mentioned in feature 1.

Appendix E.4: Peculiar complicated spectral features in the spectra of YHG

Interesting observations, discussions and summaries about rare, and peculiar complicated spectral features were discussed and summarized by Gorlova et al. (2006) and in Klochkova (2019). Sometimes they are atypical of YHG and due to explosion flashes by the presence of hot nearby sources, or in the atmosphere either in an outer shell. The observed features are for example, complex hydrogen absorption and emission profiles, such like in the envelope of HR 8752 (Sargent 1965; Luck 1975; Lambert & Luck 1978), and highly excited forbidden emissions in the spectra, such as [N II] lines in the spectrum of HR 8752, and in

the spectrum of HR 5171A obtained in 1971 and 1972 by Warren (1973), its outburst occurred in 1973.

Appendix E.5: More information on HR 5171A and Fig. E.6

1.- The three red bars at the bottom of Fig. E.6 mark the epochs of the H -band images made by Wittkovski et al. (2017 a, b, and c). These images suggest a variable circumference of the photosphere, but a more plausible explanation is that it is caused by the instable NIR H -band radiating layer. We claim that HR 5171A is not a RSG, but a genuine YHG and at a shorter distance than so far assumed (Paper I, Sect. 2.9).

2.- In the same section of Paper I we described the gradual reduction of the visual amplitudes of the pulsations of HR 5171A, until the last observed minimum called the Blown-minimum in August 2015 (marked by the red arrow to the left). At the time, pulsations appeared to decrease from the end of 2016 to early 2018. This happened 16 y after the last outburst in 2000, called the Otero-minimum by Chesneau et al. (2013) in their Fig. 3.

Because of the exciting experience with HR 8752 of which the time history was extensively studied by Nieuwenhuijzen et al. (2012), and some in this paper. We decided to check the present stability of HR 5171A as well.

Table E.2. Dates, amplitudes, durations and intrinsic colour indexes of four ρ Cas outbursts.

	1946		2000
JD	32000	JD	51830
Ampl 1, V_{vis} , B_{PG}	~ 0.9 , ~ 1.4	Ampl 1, V , R , I ,	1.02, 0.80, 0.52
Ampl 2, V_{vis} , B_{PG}	~ 1.1 , ~ 1.2	Ampl 2, V 0.6 ^a , -, -	
		Ampl 3, V ,	0.4 ^b ,
Dmin	400 d	Dmin	< 50 d
D1	320 d	D1	230 d
D2	400 d	D2	170 d ^c
D _{outb}	720 d	D _{outb}	400 d
		D3	(225) d ^d
$(B - V)_0$ LTV	~ 1.0	$(B - V)_0$ LTV	(0.9) ^e
	min 1986		min 2013
JD	46530	JD	56600
Ampl 1, V , B	~ 0.7 , 1.0	Ampl 1, V , B	~ 0.50 , ~ 0.80
Ampl 2, V , B	0.9, -	Ampl 2, V , B	0.50, 0.66
Dmin	100 d	Dmin	< 55 d
D1	255 d	D1	170 d
D2	320 d	D2	360 d
D _{outb}	575 d	D _{outb} 530 d	
$(B - V)_0$ LTV	1.0	$(B - V)_0$ LTV	0.8
$(U - B)_0$ LTV	0.8		

Notes. The 1946 outburst: see Figs. G.1. & H.1. Ampl 1, 2 = amplitude between minimum (min1) and the two maxima: max1 and max2, respectively. Ampl 3 = amplitude of the pulsation (max3) directly after max2, without a normal pulsation minimum in between. D min = approximate duration of the minimum brightness measured at a distance of ~ 0.1 m from the minimum brightness. D 1, 2 = time interval between min1 and the outburst max1 and between min1 and max2, respectively. D 3 = time interval between max2 and the neighbouring max3. D_{outb} = D 1 + D 2. The intrinsic median colour index $(B - V)_0$ (LTV) are indicated in boldface. ^(a) Represents max 2: observed visually (V_{vis}) by the AAVSO and the French Association of Variable Star Observers. Light curve depicted in Fig. 1 of Lobel et al. 2003. ^(b) Represents max 3. See^a. ^(c) See^a. ^(d) See^a. ^(e) Due to a lack of observations, the trend of the $(B - V)_0$ of the LTV during the outburst episode, had to be extrapolated.

The result for HR 5171A, prepared by E.B. as depicted in Fig. E.6, by R.T. who was responsible for the one-standard deviation grey band. Thus, the diagram depicts the 2016-2018 interval with very weak pulsation amplitudes, which appeared to be a coincidence, as thereafter a normal pulsation cadence became prominent again. Nevertheless, the importance of this light curve of HR 5171A is unaffected, as any time series offers new information on the instability history. This light curve based on visual estimates was only possible by the tenacity and enthusiasm of the 16 colleagues, see Table 1.

Appendix F: In pursuit of the solution

Appendix F.1: Summary and a general image of the information offered by the four panels

The fulfilment of the question how one can recognize radial pulsations and how important they are for the onset of outbursts, we refer to the second paragraph of Sect. 8.3 in the main text, starting with: ‘It is not always easy to decide...’ In Fig. 7, we witness a gradual change to the 1986-outburst, about 15 y before the best studied 2000-outburst (Lobel et al. 2003), of the global arrangement of pulsations along a blue track, periods short, star small with many non-radial atmospheric movements. The hypergiant cannot quickly lose its energy, and the best way is to pulsate more radially up to the outburst, which appeared to be the case as suspected by Lobel et al. (2003). This suspicion is supported by the fact that a few cycles prior to the 2000-outburst, these pulsations also showed enhanced mass-loss episodes.

Consequently, their $(B - V)$ -values are relatively red by the selective continuum opacity: in B more than in V , (Paper I: in Sect. 2.6 and in its Appendix D & E). As soon as the V_{rad} measurements show globally sufficiently strong expanding atmospheric pulsations, the same will be the case for the very last contraction and compression phase; star relatively small, see Fig. 7: Nos. 21(1)-21(3)) in the third panel. It is hot with respect to previous pulsation maxima, ~ 7500 K, according to the first panel.

Returning to the best studied case, the 2000-outburst, see the compressed star No. 15(1) in the third panel, after contraction the atmospheric layers rebound and cool, while hydrogen H^+ -recombination synchronously reinforces a rapid atmospheric expansion phase, causing a global mechanical type of strong pulsation or outburst, leading to a deep brightness minimum min1: No. 15(2) (third panel), and showing the largest radius of $750 R/R_{\odot}$ while the temperature is cool according to the first panel of $T_{\text{eff}} \sim 4500$ K. By that time almost all partially ionized hydrogen gas has become neutral, and this release of ionization-recombination energy drives an episode of strong mass-loss (Lobel et al. 2003). After an outburst, or episode with large mass-loss, ρ Cas contracts along a blue track, while its pulsations switch-over to decreasing non-radial pulsations.

The hotter characteristic points of the 2013-outburst (first panel), are well visible, just like all individual neighbouring T_{eff} datapoints in Fig. 3 of Kraus et al. (2019). Although a genuine temperature for max1 was lacking, the estimated one, represented by the bracketed red dot in the first panel, was likely more than 8000 K. After all, its max-

Table F.1. Data for the four panels of Fig. 7, counted from the bottom to the top panel.

Red. JD	T_{eff} K	$LTV(B - V)_{\text{obs}}$	R/R_{\odot}	$P(\text{d})$	n	Notes
38.00	6870	1.10	380			
39.40	6870	1.10	380			
40.00	7115	1.05	345	275	9	
41.50	7115	1.05	345			
42.00	6568	1.12	402	377	6	
44.30	6708	1.35	407	475	2	
44.80	6595	1.35	413			
46.30	7242	1.34	360			max1 1986
46.40	6070	1.45	433			median 1986
46.53	4648	1.55	759	590	2	min1 1986
46.85	7780	1.30	352			max2 1986
46.90	6775	1.40	400			
47.50	6435	1.38	431	292	4	
47.90	6755	1.36	375			
48.40	6848	1.25	389	217	3	
48.50	6718	1.25	398			
49.00	7052	1.20	366			
49.50	6488	1.44	427			
50.20	6080	1.45	437	362	5	
51.00	6400	1.45	435			
51.50	6238	1.45	439			
51.60	7600	1.32	363			max1 2000
51.70	5848	1.47	466			median 2000
51.83	4410	1.53	773	400	2	min1 2000
52.00	6788	1.33	363			max2 2000
53.00	6262	1.25	451			
53.40	6508	1.28	415	234	4	
54.00	6522	1.15	415			
54.50	6658	1.12	398	298	4	
55.00	6845	1.10	377			
55.10				335	2	
55.40	6450	1.22	421			
55.50	6680	1.22	391	450	2	
55.90	6865	1.20	368	450	2	
56.10	6945	1.17	370			
56.30				270	2	
56.40	8150	1.10	319			max1 2013
56.50	6362	1.30	433			median 2013
56.60	4900	1.42	701	535	2	min1 2013
57.00	7302	1.21	363			max2 2013
56.80	6815	1.30	382			
57.10	6610	1.25	400	335	2	
57.50	6835	1.23	384			
57.60	6872	1.25	391	550	2	
58.05	6885	1.25	385	400	2	
59.00	6670	1.26	404			

Notes. The parameter n in the sixth column represents the number of pulsations used for the average of $P(\text{d})$ listed below in the fifth column. Two empty columns below, with the exception for $P(\text{d})$ and n , concern two atypical peaks plotted close to the green ellipse in the fourth panel on the right, for which no other reliable parameters could be derived.

imum visual brightness was also higher than for the individual adjacent maxima max0 and max2. Also a few high temperatures were computed using the 4T method, for a number of BV -datapoints of G.W.H. They belong to a missing pulsation with a light maximum max-1 at about JD 24 55700.

Appendix G: The PG, VIS and AAVSO-visual time series of ρ Cas 1885-1963

First we analyze the data sets 1905-1963 (see also Table 1). These tables list the individual simplified photographic (PG) and visual (VIS) datapoints as depicted in Fig. G.1. ‘Simplified’ means that we read off the magnitudes at strategic points, viz. for the PG pulsations the maxima, the minima, and in some cases one or more along the ascending and descending branches, and for the VIS

Fig. E.3. The three two-colour diagram of the 2000-outburst episode based on the light-curves depicted in Fig. E.2 (Table 1.), corrected for the interstellar reddening (Table 1 of Paper I). Dashed portions are gaps in the time-series.

pulsations one or two points along the ascending and declining branches of the pulsations. They often represent the mean of a number of observations. It also means that all individual pulsations are still recognisable; see the black dots in Fig. G.1. In this way these light-curves are much more surveyable than the original ones. See for more details Appendix G.1.

Appendix G.1: The construction of Fig. G.1 and the analysis of the PG, VIS, and AAVSO - VIS light-curves

Appendix G.1.1: The construction

The PG light-curve is based on two papers from Payne-Gaposhkin & Mayall (1947; P-G& M 1947), of which we did not use the few observations between 1885-1904. However, we return to discuss them at a later moment in Appendix H.2. The second paper is by Gaposhkin (1949; G 1949). Both papers include the 1946 outburst. The genuine individual PG observations are usually averages of a number of observations (1-5 or more). The spread in their plotted averages varies between $\pm 0^m05$ and $\pm 0^m1$.

The VIS light-curve consists of two different types of observations. The first ones are visual (VIS) observations which started in 1904 until 1934 by many observers and painstakingly discussed and analyzed by Hassenstein (1934) and presented on the Berlin-Potsdamer scale. The way of observing at the time was quite different from the AAVSO

Table G.1. Individual virtual data points in magnitudes for Fig. G.1 of the PG-lightcurve of 1905-1947 of ρ Cas. (reduced JDs).

JD	PG	JD	PG	JD	PG
16400	6.0	21200	5.62	27500	3.6
16500	5.7	21300	5.9	27850	5.8
16510	6.2	21450	5.76	28100	5.6
16520	6.0	21600	6.0	28250	5.78
16530	6.6	21900	5.52	28400	5.6
16900	6.0	22050	5.95	28600	5.77
17000	6.5	22300	5.65	28850	5.65
17250	5.66	22400	5.95	28950	5.52
17300	6.3	22550	5.8	29100	5.79
17500	5.7	22600	6.0	29200	5.66
17600	5.96	22700	5.9	29350	5.85
17650	5.62	22800	6.05	29600	5.7
17700	5.96	23000	5.7	29950	5.8
17800	6.3	23100	5.8	30100	5.65
18100	5.58	23300	5.5	30200	5.8
18200	5.9	23400	5.8	30250	5.87
18400	5.5	23500	6.4	30400	6.04
18600	6.2	23650	5.5	30500	5.74
18800	5.7	23900	5.9	30700	6.16
18850	6.0	24150	5.64	30750	6.18
19000	6.2	24250	5.76	30800	5.95
19150	5.85	24400	5.66	30900	5.7
19250	6.0	24550	5.76	31100	5.9
19400	5.42	24650	5.76	31300	6.4
19500	5.58	24900	5.68	31350	6.35
19600	5.4	25000	5.9	31380	5.9
19650	5.9	25100	5.68	31400	6.3
19800	5.65	25250	5.87	31480	6.6
19900	5.98	25400	5.58	31500	5.8
20000	5.7	25500	5.78	31550	5.7
20050	5.98	25750	5.6	31650	5.6
20100	5.7	26000	5.75	31750	5.7
20250	5.84	26300	5.62	31900	6.88
20450	5.57	26550	5.75	32000	6.9
20600	5.8	26750	5.5	32250	6.86
20700	5.38	26800	5.7	32300	5.85
20950	5.7	27000	5.45	32350	5.74
20800	5.6	27100	5.79	32400	5.9
20900	5.6	27250	5.45	32450	5.76
20950	5.9	27350	5.76		

observations in 1941-1963, including the 1946 outburst. The spread in Hassenstein's collected individual VIS observations is much smaller than the spread in the AAVSO VIS observations 1941-1963 ($\pm 0^m5$) of which only averages are plotted in Fig. G.1. The accuracy of the VIS observations (mainly those of Hassenstein) is better than the accuracy of the PG points. The mysterious VIS brightness decline 1919-1920/1921 causes a lack in yellow light by 0^m4 . No observations were made between 1934 and 1941. The LTVs of all pulsations in both panels, including the 1946 outburst, are represented by the unsteady lines.

Appendix G.1.2: A comparison of the magnitude scales between VIS and V (Johnson system)

The LTV of the VIS pulsations of Hassenstein 1904-1919 is represented by the black dashed/dotted line 1905-1919-

Fig. E.4. This diagram depicts the shortening of the quasi-periods of HR 8752. The decline of the quasi-periods (from 600 d to 100 d) of HR 8752 between 1976 and 1994 runs surprisingly linear and started after the 1973 outburst. Observers and other information listed in Table 1. ΔD represents the duration of every single pulsation represented by a single line. Its length matches the number of days on the JD axis below. The bracketed line piece with a supposed pulsation cycle of about 450 d could as well consist of two cycles: of about 225 d (by optical illusion the lower cycle looks shorter than the upper cycle). The two line pieces with a question mark, represent pulsation cycles badly covered with observations.

1963, but neglecting the AAVSO VIS observations with the 1946-outburst. It ends at $VIS = 4^m5$. The LTV of V (Johnson system) is depicted in Fig. 11 of Paper I, and starts in 1965 at about 4^m5 , and runs almost horizontally to 1979.

Conclusion: the VIS and the V (Johnson system) magnitudes are almost equal within an uncertainty of about 0^m1 .

Appendix G.1.3: A comparison of the magnitude scales of PG and B (Johnson system)

A straight line sketched through all PG pulsations from the min1 of 1905 up to 1963 ends at about $PG = 5^m7$. The LTV of B (Johnson system) depicted in Fig. 11 of Paper I starts in 1965 with $B = 5^m6$, slightly declining to 1979 with $B = 5^m8$.

Conclusion: the PG and B (Johnson system) magnitude scale are almost equal within an uncertainty of about 0^m1 .

Appendix G.1.4: The AAVSO VIS brightness excess from 1941 and back to normal at 1957

The LTV of the AAVSO VIS observations 1941-1963 is also represented by the unsteady line. It starts in 1941 higher than the normal VIS brightness 1905-1919-1963, rep-

resented by the dashed/dotted line. After the 1946 outburst it declines and runs constant from about 1957 (reduced JD 36.25) to $VIS = 4^m8$, showing a VIS brightness lack by $\sim 0^m3$. However, it is common knowledge that the AAVSO visual brightness estimates are about $0^m3 \pm 0^m1$ weaker than the V -magnitude (Johnson system), thus also with VIS magnitudes as both magnitude scales (V and the VIS) are equal (see Appendix G.1.2).

Consequently, shift the LTV of the AAVSO light curve 1941-1963 upward by 0^m3 , see dotted LTV labeled: 'corrected LTV(AAVSO)' (accidentally crossing the top of the first pulsation). Surprisingly, the fading of yellow light 1920-1934 is then exchanged for a brightness excess by roughly the same amount which started somewhere between 1934 and 1941. Obviously, the yellow light radiating layer fell back and became temporarily compressed. This might have caused the temporarily brightness excess. This excess gradually fades away until zero in 1957 (reduced JD.36.25) with $VIS = 4^m5$, and the atmosphere of ρ Cas is back to normal like between 1905-1919.

Conclusions:

The analysis of the VIS observations was much more complicated due to a sudden mysterious brightness decline in the VIS data in 1919 amounting to 0^m4 , (leaving PG magnitudes unaffected), and staying constant until some-

Fig. E.5. The time series 2017-2023 of HR 8752 in B , V , and $(B - V)$ (Johnson system) relative to the comparison star. The trend of light and colour index is constant from 2017 to 2023. See the light and colour curves of the discoverers E.J.v.B. and M.S. Photoelectric observations of E.J.v.B. are represented by large dots, CCD observations by M.S. by small dots. They are relative to the comparison star (c) HR 8761 with $V = 6.202$, $B = 7.702$, and $(B - V) = 1.500$. It is obvious that the pulsation activity of HR 8752 stopped somewhere after 1996 and before 2017 see Fig. E.4 (also Nieuwenhuijzen et al. 2012). Standard deviations according to M.S. for $B = 0^m05$, for $V = 0^m035$, for $(B - V) = 0^m04$. It appears that the 2017-2023 observed photometric parameters amount to: $V_{\text{obs}} = 5.30$, $B_{\text{obs}} = 6.15$, and $(B - V)_{\text{obs}} = 0.85$. Just as ρ Cas in Fig. A.2, the HR 8752 parameters are not much different from the extrapolations of the medians plotted in Figs. 6. & 7. for HR 8752 in Paper I.

Table G.2. Individual virtual data points in magnitudes for Fig. G.1. of the VIS light curve 1905-1934 of ρ Cas. (JDs are reduced)

JD	VIS												
16450	4.56	18000	4.36	19450	4.36	20400	4.50	21850	4.58	23600	4.72	25300	4.76
16500	4.45	18010	4.36	19500	4.28	20500	4.08	21950	4.34	23700	4.70	25400	4.76
16600	4.5	18250	4.66	19550	4.25	20550	4.36	22050	4.78	23800	4.76	25600	4.82
16700	4.56	18300	4.61	19600	4.46	20600	4.56	22300	4.66	23850	4.81	25700	4.90
16750	4.75	18400	4.22	19650	4.52	20700	4.36	22400	4.66	23950	4.87	25900	4.76
16850	4.84	18500	4.50	19700	4.50	20750	4.55	22500	4.76	24100	4.71	26000	4.82
16900	4.76	18550	4.76	19800	4.41	20800	4.26	22650	4.95	24200	4.80	26100	4.96
17000	4.45	18600	4.76	19850	4.41	20900	4.60	22700	5.15	24220	4.91	26200	4.76
17050	4.25	18750	4.50	20000	4.50	21000	4.47	22800	4.71	24250	4.86	26250	4.96
17250	4.26	18800	4.42	20050	4.67	21100	4.50	23000	4.70	24400	4.71	26400	4.80
17350	4.30	18900	4.55	20100	4.60	21150	4.42	23100	4.71	24450	4.86	26600	4.76
17450	4.17	19000	4.80	21150	4.41	21300	4.50	23300	4.70	24550	4.76	26650	4.86
17500	4.20	19050	4.72	20170	4.46	21550	4.50	23350	4.87	24650	4.76	26800	4.75
17550	4.45	19200	4.46	20200	4.50	21650	4.60	23450	5.00	24750	4.76	26900	4.95
17800	4.50	19300	4.46	20300	4.42	21750	4.42	23500	4.96	24850	4.70	27000	4.66
17900	4.70	19400	4.36	20350	4.55	21800	4.50	23550	4.78	24900	4.75	27050	4.76
27150	5.00	27200	4.80	27300	4.92	27400	4.92	27500	4.82				

where between 1934 and 1941, when it was apparently replaced by a brightness excess of about 0^m3 (thus, the total rise amounted to $0^m4 + 0^m3 = 0^m7$. The original brightness decline 0^m4 in 1919 was restored between 1934 and 1941). The VIS gradually faded away until about 1957. It should be noted that Hassenstein (1934) considered this decline as

real. The cause of the V -brightness decline may be related to some shell expansion event for which only longer wavelengths in the spectrum are sensitive. When the shell fall back between 1934 and 1941, the density temporarily increased explaining the temporarily brightness excess fading away in 1957.

Fig. E.6. Visual light curve of HR 5171A prepared by E.B., based on more than 800 estimates from Aug 2015 to Jan 2022). The Blown-minimum is marked by the red arrow. The six green dots are the photoelectric V -observation of G.D.S. They are as usual brighter than the visual estimates by about 0^m3 , the latter should be shifted upward to fit the photoelectric ones. The gray band around the oscillating median between 2015 and 2022 has a width of one standard deviation of the local spread, it was the responsibility of R.T. See Table 1. for the observers. Discussion in Appendix E.5.

Appendix G.1.5: The PG and VIS dips of 1923, an outburst?

We questioned whether the 1923 PG dip (total depth 0^m8) might be an outburst, although there is no normal counterpart in the VIS light curve, apart from an unlikely shallow 0^m3 dip. However, the latter could be distorted by the lack in VIS brightness after 1919. Moreover, all pulsation amplitudes are small between 1919 and 1934. The reliability of the 1923 PG dip is unknown. It is only based on two brightness estimates. Besides the morphology of a genuine outburst looks different from this dip.

The 1923-dip in VIS is very shallow, like all pulsation amplitudes between 1923 and 1934. We wonder whether all VIS pulsation amplitudes are weakened by the same lack of brightness.

To answer this questions we made a detailed plot of Okounev's VIS pulsations from 1918/1919 until the 1923-dip (including those by Leiner, see Hassenstein 1934). It appears that there is no match whatsoever with e.g. the 2000-outburst and its preceding pulsations, despite the blue loop evolution (B) after 1923.

Conclusion:

We conclude that the PG and VIS 1923 dips are most likely not caused by an outburst.

Appendix G.1.6: The sequence of blue and red evolutionary loops

The black bars in Fig. G.1 depicted in the PG panel, represent a number of evolutionary loops. They are only based on reliable VIS and PG pulsation sequences. Three are blue (B) after the 1905 and 1923 dips (although not very convincing, thus, 1923 is likely no outburst) and after the 1946 outburst. One red R loop precedes this outburst, which is normal (see Fig. 7).

Conclusion:

Figure G.1 shows reliable blue evolutionary loops after the minI of 1905 and after 1946 (V decline very steep). A red loop precedes the 1946 outburst which is normal. The pulsations preceding the 1946-outburst show the typical pulsation period and amplitude increase like in Fig. 7, see original PG light curves by Gaposchkin (1949).

Fig. G.1. As the original photographic and visual observations made at the time are very numerous and the original light curves appear to be not suitable for a proper analysis, our light curves consists of individual 'simplified' observations from photographic (PG) observations between 1905 and 1946, from the visual observations (VIS) between 1904 and 1934, and from the AAVSO-VIS observations between 1941 and 1963.

Table G.3. Individual virtual AAVSO - VIS observations 1941-1963 including the min1 of 1946, of ρ Cas, in Fig. G.1 (JDs are reduced).

JD	AAVSO-VIS
30100	4.80
30500	4.15
30900	4.75
31000	4.60
31100	4.50
31300	4.35
31500	4.60
31750	4.50
31900	5.50
32000	5.90
32250	5.45
32350	4.65
32450	5.10
32750	4.40
32950	4.60
33100	4.42
33250	4.68
33500	4.50
33750	4.64
34000	4.50
34150	4.70
34500	4.70
34650	4.60
34950	4.57
35050	4.90
35500	4.68
35800	4.84
36000	4.62
36200	4.85
36300	4.74
36500	4.96
36700	4.96
36900	4.68
37150	4.72
37250	4.95
37500	4.75
37850	4.86

Notes. The spread in these observations is much larger than the earlier VIS observations between 1905-1934. In view of some known names, we assume that the earlier VIS observations were made by more professionally trained astronomers and amateurs. The sketched min1 of the 1946 outburst (reduced JD = 32.00) is uncertain, while below the median the fainter observations are dotted, and cannot even be used. The unsteady black lines represent real oscillations (according to our guess). The upper dotted line, labeled "corrected LTV(AAVSO)" is discussed in the text in Section 4.

Table G.4. The 1905-1934 medians of the PG and VIS observations in Fig. G.1. thus, both have the same JD (reduced).

JD	PG	VIS	JD	PG	VIS
16350	5.80	4.57	22000	5.78	4.46
16500	6.00	4.58	22150	5.79	4.60
16750	6.32	4.60	22250	5.81	4.70
16900	6.25	4.58	22350	5.83	4.78
17000	6.16	4.56	22600	5.86	4.90
17250	6.04	4.50	22750	5.85	4.90
17500	5.96	4.46	23100	5.82	4.88
17750	5.92	4.46	23300	5.84	4.88
18000	5.90	4.50	23500	5.92	4.86
18250	5.90	4.50	23750	5.84	4.83
18500	5.92	4.50	24000	5.77	4.81
18500	5.92	4.50	24550	5.74	4.80
18750	5.98	4.61	24500	5.72	4.80
19000	6.00	4.60	24750	5.74	4.80
19200	5.84	4.56	25000	5.76	4.80
19250	5.82	4.54	25250	5.74	4.81
19500	5.76	4.50	25500	5.70	4.82
19750	5.80	4.50	25750	5.71	4.84
20000	5.82	4.52	26000	5.70	4.85
20250	5.76	4.42	26250	5.69	4.85
20500	5.65	4.38	26500	5.67	4.86
20700	5.60	4.46	26750	5.64	4.86
21000	5.74	4.48	27000	5.62	4.86
21250	5.80	4.52	27250	5.62	4.86
21500	5.84	4.53	27500	5.69	4.88
21750	5.80	4.48			

Notes. The next Table G.5. only represent the median of the PG observations 1934-1947

Table G.5. The 1934-1947 median of the PG lightcurve in Fig. G.1. (Reduced JDs)

JD	PG	Notes
27750	5.72	
28500	5.70	
29000	5.70	
29750	5.80	
30500	5.92	
31350	6.06	
31750	6.24	MED 1946
32300	6.24	MED 1946
32400	6.22	MED 1946
32500	6.20	

Table G.6. The median of the 1941-1963 AAVSO - VIS lightcurve in Fig. G.1. (Reduced JDs)

JD	VIS	Notes
30230	4.50	
30800	4.50	
31000	4.58	
31500	4.82	
31650	4.90	
31750	4.95	
32000	4.95	MED 1946
32250	4.94	MED 1946
32400	4.90	
32550	4.80	
32750	4.68	
32900	4.55	
33750	4.60	
34250	4.62	
34550	4.66	
34950	4.74	
35250	4.76	
36000	4.76	
36250	4.80	
36700	4.80	
38000	4.80	

**Appendix H: The LTV of $(B - V)_{\text{obs}}$ of the
1904-1987 time series of ρ Cas**

Table H.1. Data for the $(B - V)_{\text{obs}}$ versus Red.JD diagram of ρ Cas 1904-1987.

Red. JD	$(B - V)_{\text{obs}}$	
16.35	1.08	Red loop 1904 to min1 1905
16.50	1.27	
16.75	1.57	Blue loop from min1 1905 to R1
16.90	1.52	
17.00	1.45	
17.25	1.38	
17.50	1.35	
17.75	1.32	
18.00	1.25	
18.25	1.25	
18.50	1.27	
18.75	1.22	
19.00	1.25	
19.20	1.13	
19.25	1.13	
19.50	1.11	
19.75	1.15	
20.00	1.15	
20.50	1.12	
20.75	1.19	
20.70	0.99	Red loop R1 to 1919
21.00	0.99	
21.25	1.13	
21.50	1.16	
21.75	1.15	
21.95	1.17	
22.10	1.15	VIS brightness decline 1919-1921
22.15	1.04	
22.25	0.96	
22.35	0.90	
22.60	0.81	
22.75	0.90	
23.10	0.79	Red loop R2 to 1923
23.30	0.81	
23.75	0.86	Blue loop to 1934
24.00	0.81	
24.25	0.79	
24.50	0.77	
24.75	0.79	
25.00	0.81	
25.25	0.78	
25.50	0.73	
25.75	0.72	
26.00	0.70	
26.25	0.69	
26.50	0.66	
26.75	0.63	
27.00	0.61	
27.25	0.61	
27.50	0.66	
30.23	1.24	Red loop R3 1941-1942 to 1946 outburst,
31.00	1.30	with four corrected AAVSO datapoints
31.50	1.33	
31.65	1.34	
31.65	max1, 1946 outburst	
32.00	med	
32.00	min1	
32.35	max2	
38.80	1.10	1963 to 1986

39.40	1.10	
39.40	1.10	
40.50	1.05	
41.50	1.05	
42.00	1.12	
44.29	1.35	
44.80	1.35	
46.26	1.34	max1 1986
46.50	1.55	min1
46.50	1.45	med
46.85	1.30	max2
46.90	1.40	Blue loop to 1987
47.50	1.38	

Table H.1. Data for the $(B - V)_{\text{obs}}$ versus reduced JD diagram of ρ Cas 1904-1987.

Fig. H.1. The LTV of $(B - V)_{\text{obs}}$ 1904-1986 of ρ Cas vs. the reduced JD, of which B represents the PG magnitudes and V the VIS magnitudes, see Appendix G.1.3 and Appendix G.1.4. The outburst of 1905 is only represented by min1, while those of 1946 and 1986 (also present in Fig. 7) are complete and are represented by max1: the first blue circles on the left of the outburst, then min1 and max2. Estimated errors: for 1905 and 1946 $\pm 0^m2$, for 1986 $\pm 0^m05$. As the PG magnitudes stop right after 1946, we cannot derive $(B - V)_{\text{obs}}$ values anymore.

Appendix H.1: The discussion on the LTV of $(B - V)_{\text{obs}}$ versus the reduced JD diagram of ρ Cas 1904-1986

Figure H.1 depicts the LTV of $(B - V)_{\text{obs}}$ based on the transformation from the photographic (PG) and visual (VIS) observations including one (1905), and three (1946 and 1986) characteristic points, to B and V magnitudes, respectively. We stress that ‘observed’ means that by plotting ordinary datapoints and the four characteristic points of outbursts, the lack and the excess of the VIS-brightness are always included.

1.-The diagram starts with a steep red track preceding the 1905 dip. The high $(B - V)_{\text{obs}}$ -value suggests an outburst. In the original figure by Payne-Gaposhkin & Mayall (1947) the PG observations between 1902 and 1906 show a wavy pattern due to a number of successive dips and peaks, presumably by ordinary pulsations, but the uncertainty is large. The minimum brightness in 1905 amounts to $PG = 6.6$, while the one of 1946-outburst by Payne-Gaposhkin & Mayall (1947) and Gaposhkin (1949) as shown by Lobel et al. (2003, Fig. 13. being more reliable), amounts to $PG = 6.9$. Obviously there is some resemblance. According to Payne-Gaposhkin & Mayall the spectral type halfway the ascending branch of the 1904-1905 minimum is K5, while the one at min1 of 1946 min1 by Gaposhkin (1949) it is M5 p. as the temperature is lower. We conclude that also 1905 is an outburst. This is supported by the blue track after 1905 until the red track R1 (Figs. G.1 and H.1).

2.- The red track R1 runs until 1919, the date of the sudden decline of the VIS-brightness by $0^{\text{m}}4$ to 1921 in Fig. G.1. The resulting blue track is represented by the blue dots and the plus-signs. After the short red track R2 the bluing continues to 1934, being too blue due to the lack of the VIS brightness (see Fig. 7.), due to the blue track evolution by the PG observations (Fig. G.1). During the 1934-1941 gap in the time-series ρ Cas became subject to the VIS brightness excess discussed in Appendix G.1.4. This is illustrated by the dashed line (no observations available) to the red track R3 which starts in 1941 with four ‘corrected LTV(AAVSO)’ ordinary datapoints ending in 1946, as the uncertainty in of the four ordinary datapoints amount to $\pm 0^{\text{m}}1$. Because the four characteristic points of the 1946-outburst cannot be accurately located either, the uncertainty of the $(B - V)_{\text{obs}}$ in Fig. H.1 amounts to $\pm 0^{\text{m}}1 - 0^{\text{m}}2$.

The reason is the absence of PG observations (thus, no B -magnitudes). Apart from this the VIS excess is included by about the same amount as the lack of the VIS brightness between 1919 and 1934. This causes a too red location for the 1946 outburst as depicted in Fig. H.1.

The LTV of $(B - V)_{\text{obs}}$ restarts in 1963 and ends in 1987 on a blue track after the 1986-outburst.

Appendix H.2: The inspection of the PG light curve 1885-1902 for earlier outbursts

About a dozen PG observations with low weight by Payne-Gaposhkin & Mayall (1947) show from 1885 small scatter between $5^{\text{m}}6 - 6^{\text{m}}0$, while the few spectral types hover between F8 and K0. However, in 1895/1896 three low-weight observations are weaker with a minimum $6^{\text{m}}4$. Two spectral classes indicate K0p and the faintest one; K5p. Obviously we are dealing with the very first outburst known.

Appendix H.3: The sequence of known outbursts of ρ Cas between 1885 and 2013

The complete sequence of six outbursts 1895, 1905, 1946, 1986, 2000, and 2013 between 1885-2013 shows no special pattern with respect to the time intervals. They look arbitrary: 10-41-40-14-13 years, respectively.

Note: In Section 8.2. we discuss a most interesting discovery that the T_{eff} of the sequence of ordinary eruptions from the first (young: e.g.1905) ones to the last ones (old: e.g. 2013) increase, for max1 as well as for min1.